

Accord University

Knowledge & Vision

TITLE: A cross-sectional survey of biological hazards among healthcare workers in Garowe General Hospital.

This dissertation is submitted as partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of the Master of *Tropical Medicine and Infectious Diseases* (TMIDs) from **Accord University - Somalia.**

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April 13, 2023

Declaration:

I, Mohamed Ali Isse, declare that the work presented in this research report is my original work and has never been presented to any institution before for any award. I, therefore, present it for the Award of a Master of Tropical Medicine and Infectious Disease.

Approval page:

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'D. Odulusi', is written over a horizontal dotted line. A solid black line is drawn below the dotted line, extending from the left side of the signature towards the right.

Dr. Daniel Odulusi.

Dedication:

This thesis is dedicated to my beloved parents as they have brought me up, and taught me, and they are the reason I reached this level. May Allah have mercy on them in this world, and bring them to Paradise Hereafter. It is also dedicated to my wife and children, and also to my brothers and sisters and my friends.

Acknowledgment:

First of all, all Praise belongs to Allah, who has conveyed to me this position I am in today. Secondly, I appreciate my parents, my wife, my children, and my friends for their encouragement during this course. May the Almighty Allah richly reward you abundantly.

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Mohamed Ali Isse

April 13, 2023.

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ABSTRACT.

Background: Biological hazards, the most significant risks in health settings, especially infections, are among the most important risks for healthcare workers in hospitals. **Problem Statement:** With biological hazards threatening the health and life of HCWs globally and regionally, the situation in Somalia is worse, and there are not enough studies done to determine how far the problem is reaching. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to fill-partially this gap. **Significance of the Study:** This study is important for researchers and students who are studying the same topic. the study is also essential for policymakers and hospital managers to know the significant burden of biological hazards among HCWs, and to take appropriate action for the safety and well-being of HCWs. **Methodology:** This was a cross-sectional descriptive study design employing quantitative methods of data collection. The target population for the study was the HCWs of the Garowe General Hospital. We select 65 respondents from 86 of the total hospital staff. The instrument of the study was standardized, validated, and a self-administered questionnaire. The data were analyzed by the SPSS and the **Results** showed that 43.1% of participants experienced blood. 35.4% of the respondents were exposed to NSIs. 36.9% were exposed to Droplet/airborne infections. 50.8% of the participants reported exposure to infectious diseases such as HB, HC, HIV/AIDS, TB, and Influenza infections. 96.9% said all PPE is available at the hospital. 95.4% utilize all necessary PPE. **Recommendations:** All HCWs should receive periodic courses on universal health and safety precautions. They must vaccinate against vaccine-preventable diseases. Post-exposure prophylaxis and Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) should be made available for them. Health settings should have adequate medical waste disposal systems.

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List of abbreviations or acronyms:

ALT.....	Alanine Aminotransferase
ARTI.....	Annual Rate of Tuberculosis Infection
AIDS.....	acquired immunodeficiency syndrome
BCG.....	Bacillus Calmette-Guerin
BSL.....	Biosafety level
CBG.....	..Canadian Biosafety Guideline
CD4.....	The cluster of differentiation 4
CDC.....	Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
COVID-19.....	Coronavirus 2019
FFP.....	Filtering facepiece
GGH.....	Garowe General Hospital
GMO.....	Genetically Modified Organisms
HAIs.....	Healthcare-Associated Infections
HBIG.....	Hepatitis B Immunoglobulin
HBsAg.....	Hepatitis B surface Antigen
HBV.....	Hepatitis B Virus
HCQ.....	Hydro-chloroquine Sulfate.
HCV.....	Hepatitis C Virus
HCWs.....	Health Care Workers

HIV	Human Immunodeficiency Viruses
HSA.....	Health and Safety Authority.
ICMR.....	Indian Council for medical research
ILI.....	Influenza-like illness
IPC.....	Infection Prevention and Control
IV.....	Intravenous
LEV.....	Local exhaust ventilation
LTBI.....	Latent Tuberculosis Infection
MDR-TB.....	Multidrug-resistant Tuberculosis
MERS.....	Middle East Respiratory Syndrome
MRSA.....	..Methicillin/oxacillin-resistant Staphylococcus aureus
NSIs.....	Needle stick injuries
PPE.....	Personal Protective Equipment
PEP.....	Postexposure Prophylaxis
RG.....	Risk group
RNA.....	Ribonucleic acid
SARS.....	Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome
TB.....	Tuberculosis
TPT.....	TB Preventive Treatment
TST.....	Tuberculin skin test

UN..... United Nations
USA..... United States of America
UVGI..... Ultraviolet Germicidal Irradiation
VRSA..... Vancomycin-resistant Staphylococcus aureus
WHO..... World Health Organization
XDR-TB..... Extensively Drug-Resistant Tuberculosis.

Chapter one

Introduction

1.0 Introduction:

1.1 Background:

Biological hazards or biohazards are organic matters that pose a high risk to the health of humans, animals, and plants ⁽¹⁾ (*Biological Hazards | Comcare*, n.d.). Biological hazards include pathogenic micro-organisms (e.g., Bacteria, viruses, parasites, fungi), poisons from biological origin, and bio-active compounds. Healthcare workers are exposed to biological hazards via contact with human bodily matter, such as blood, tissues, saliva, mucous, urine, or feces, because these substances have a high risk of containing viral or bacterial diseases, and the important routes for the transmission of infections in hospitals are bloodborne, droplet, airborne, fecal-oral, and contact routes ⁽²⁾ (Douedi, n.d.) and (Monday, 2021). The biological hazards include wounds, cuts, sharp-related injuries, direct contact with infected specimens/ biohazardous materials, bloodborne diseases, infectious diseases/infections, airborne diseases, and pollution from soiled materials ⁽³⁾ (Elewa et al., 2016). In hospitals, infections are among the most important risks for healthcare workers. Laboratory workers doctors and nurses are at risk of biohazards when collecting or handling biological materials, and when performing surgery, treating wounds, or conducting clinical exams. Also, when disinfecting, cleaning, moving contaminated equipment, or working in contaminated areas may expose hospital staff to healthcare biohazards ⁽⁴⁾ (Sacadura-Leite et al., 2018).

Globally: Worldwide, healthcare workers represent 12% of the working population ^(5, 6) (Osungbemi et al., 2016) and (Ndejjo et al., 2015). Which are nearly 60 million health workers globally. About 2/3 of them work in healthcare; and the

remaining 1/3 work in management and support. Every year about 3 million among the 35 million healthcare experts are globally exposed to pathogens originating from the blood via percutaneous routes due to professional-associated accidents. The occupational safety and health administration have declared that almost 5.5 million health specialists running in healthcare centers are highly at risk of microorganisms originating from the blood such as HCV, HBV, HIV, and different probably infectious materials. However, the implementation of risk reduction measures is suboptimal ⁽⁷⁾ (Ayenew et al., 2022). Infected HCWs may not only cause serious illness or death themselves but may spread the infection to others. The key aspect to protecting HCWs from communicable disease exposure during patient care is the proper use of personal protective equipment (PPE). PPEs include; barriers (gowns, gloves, eye shields) and respiratory protection (masks, respirators) are used to protect mucous membranes, respiratory pathways, dermal, and clothing from contact with infectious agents ⁽⁸⁾ (Casanova et al., 2008). Not wearing all necessary protective equipment and exposure to sharp injuries cause different infections including bloodborne and airborne/droplet-transmitted infections. There are over 20 blood-borne illnesses, but HBV, HCV, and HIV infections have high risks to HCWs ⁽⁹⁾ (Marković-Denić et al., 2014).

In Africa: Biohazards in Sub-Saharan Africa, are mostly underreported because of inadequate research, and a lack of necessary expertise and resources to manage them. Masum et al. observed that the growth in occupational health risks in growing nations is in large part blamed on Healthcare Workers (HCWs) not practicing standard safety precautions inclusive of hand washing, wearing gloves, and use of Protective Personal Equipment (PPE) ⁽¹⁰⁾ (Osaretin Owie & Apanga, 2016). In the Africa E sub-region (which includes Botswana, Congo, Malawi, South Africa, etc.), 11.8% of HBV, 2.8% of HCV, and 5.1% of HIV infections are because of occupational exposure. While In America A sub-region (Canada, Cuba,

United States) only 0.51% of HBV, 1.6% of HCV, and 0.29% of HIV infections are because of occupational exposure ⁽¹¹⁾ (Mossburg et al., 2019).

In Somalia: There are not been enough reports about this problem in Somalia since the central government collapsed three decades. Some local scholars made modest studies, and one of them shows that nearly half of the health workers in Borama hospitals do not wear protective clothing while dealing with medical wastes, while less than half only 47.64% use gloves always. 40.94% of them did not know the safe handling of sharp medical waste ⁽¹²⁾ (Omer Sheikh Mohamed, 2013). Another study for COVID-19 vaccination coverage for Somali healthcare workers conducted between December 2021 to January 2022 found that 48.7% of the healthcare workers were vaccinated for COVID-19 at least once. This was lower than coverage in developed countries such as the United States 83.3%, and developing countries such as Ethiopia 62.1% ⁽¹³⁾ (Dahie et al., 2022).

1.2. Problem Statement

Biological hazards are neglected public health affairs among healthcare workers in low-and-middle-income countries and expose them to different types of risks that negatively impact their health and ability to work. Biohazard injuries are taken into consideration to be the main events because of the extreme risk they pose to the wellness of healthcare workers ⁽¹⁴⁾ (Tejada-Pérez et al. 2022). The use of personal protective equipment is the most important action for preventing healthcare workers from exposure to workplace hazards, particularly in developing countries where occupational safety control instructions and principles remain a challenge to perform. The use of personal protective equipment is ordered by the “OSHA” for healthcare workers to prevent infection with blood-borne diseases such as human immunodeficiency. Healthcare providers are frequently exposed to many forms of

infectious agents while doing their duties, which may be preventable if healthcare workers comply with appropriate precautions ⁽⁴⁾ (Elewa et al., 2016).

In Somalia, the situation could be more serious and more dangerous due to the lack of acts and principles, and more than that lack of legislation, institutions, and agencies monitoring the management and safety standard protections for healthcare workers. As we know, healthcare management systems have not been operating in Somalia for more than three decades. So due to the inadequate supply of personal protective equipment, lack of training on occupational health-related hazards and protective measures, and ignorance of health and safety measures, there should be a great-health problem caused by biological hazards among healthcare workers. Safety measures and risk reduction strategies in Somalia are nearly-absent due to resource limitations. This causes Somalia to face a shortage of healthcare workers as a part of the problem. There are not enough studies done determining how far the problem is reaching. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to fill-partially this gap by gaining an understanding of the common biological hazards, availability of personal protective equipment, and their utilization practice by the healthcare workers in *Garowe General Hospital, Somalia*.

1.3 General Objective / Aim / Purpose

The aim of this literature is what biological hazards are among healthcare workers in *Garowe General Hospital*.

1.4 Specific objectives

1- To investigate or determine the common biological hazards among health workers in *Garowe General Hospital*

2- To identify the availability of Personal protective equipment (PPE) for health workers in the different departments of the hospital.

3- To assess the utilization of the PPEs by the health workers in *Garowe General Hospital*.

1.5 Research Questions

1. What are the common biological hazards that healthcare workers are exposed to at the workplace?
2. What is the availability of PPEs for health workers in the hospital?
3. What is the utilization of PPEs by health workers?

1.6 Hypotheses

Biological hazards exist where medical care is provided and the providers are at increased risk of infections. The Biological hazard that healthcare workers may expose to in the hospitals mostly are infections, such as bloodborne, airborne/droplet transmitted, and fecal-oral infections. So, it is necessary to healthcare workers to follow safety measures standards and use personal protective equipment (PPE). There is a relationship between the availability and utilization of PPE and biological hazard prevalence among healthcare workers in their workplaces. Therefore, if there is a shortage or lack of PPEs, the risk of biological hazard increases, also, if PPEs are available but the HCWs are not utilizing or not using them properly the risk of biological hazard increases. The purpose of this thesis is to investigate the biological hazards that GGH healthcare workers are exposed to and the availability and utilization of PPE.

1.7 Significance of the Study.

Biological hazards are public health affairs that are neglected by healthcare professionals in developing countries. This exposes HCWs in low-and-middle-income countries, to different types of hazards that negatively impact their health and ability to work. In hospitals, biological hazards, especially infections, are among the most important hazards for healthcare workers. Healthcare workers care for patients in the most unsafe work environment, however, some healthcare workers in developing countries are unaware of exposure and do not wear all necessary protective equipment, so they are vulnerable to biological hazards, even if they are aware of potential biological hazards, personal protective equipment (PPEs) and other safety devices to reduce biological hazards may not be available. In Somalia, there is a problem related to the risk of biological hazards in leading hospitals because of a lack/shortage of personal protective equipment availability, proper sanitation, and medical waste disposal management. Also, there is not enough research on this topic. So, this study is important for researchers and students who are studying the same topic. It can help them to further enhance their research by studying my thesis. The study is also essential for policymakers and hospital managers to know the significant burden of biological hazards among HCWs, and to take appropriate action for the safety and well-being of HCWs,

1.8 Scope of the Study:

Time of the scope: This study was conducted in the period between March 2023 to April 2023.

Geographical Scope: This study was conducted in *Garowe General Hospital, Garowe, Somalia*.

Content of the Scope: This study will focus on biological hazards among healthcare workers in *Garowe General Hospital, Garowe-Puntland- Somalia*, the study will specifically focus on the biological hazards among health workers in Garowe General Hospital, the availability of Personal protective equipment, and the wearing of necessary personal protective equipment (PPE); by the health workers.

1.9 Definition of Key Terms

Healthcare workers are defined; as all people engaged in activities; whose primary intention is to improve health. For this study, healthcare workers are those in primary contact with the patients. These include nurses, nurse assistants, midwives, intern doctors, specialists, laboratorians, and also; those who work in cleanliness.

Biological hazard: or biohazard is an organic substance that constitutes a danger to the health of humans, and other living things, caused by medical waste, microorganisms, and other biological wastes.

Personal protective equipment (PPE): refers to protective clothes (medical gowns), medical gloves, face shields, facemasks, and respirators or other equipment designed to protect the wearer from injury or the spread of infection or illness, commonly used in health settings such as hospitals ⁽¹⁵⁾ (FDA, 2020).

Garowe General Hospital (GGH): is the general public and the biggest hospital in Garowe, the capital city of *Puntland State, Somalia*.

1.10 Conceptual Framework

Independent variables _____ Dependent variable

Figure 1: Conceptual framework

1.10 Description of conceptual framework:

The above conceptual framework shows the relationship between the dependent and independent study variables. The independent variables are;

- 1- Common biological hazards among health workers
- 2- protective equipment availability
- 3- PPE utilization by the healthcare workers

The figure shows that; there's an interaction between the dependent and the independent variables and high rates of biological hazards among health workers.

CHAPTER TWO

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction:

The chapter describes the various literature reviews of other authors, which are related to the specific objectives of the study, which are the common biological hazards among healthcare workers in health facilities, Personal Protective Equipment availability, and PPE utilization by the healthcare workers in their workplaces.

2.2 Occupational Hazards in Healthcare Settings:

Many occupational hazards occur in healthcare settings, including; 1- infectious disease. 2- chemical exposure. 3- Radiation exposure. 4- Back injuries 5- Violence 6- Noise 7- Shift work 8- Repetitive strain injuries. This research; is concerned with biological hazards among healthcare workers, especially the most common ones.

2.3 Biological hazards:

2.3.1 Definition of the biological hazards:

Biological hazards are organic substances; or carried by biological vectors or sharp objects contaminated with biohazardous things that are dangerous to the health of humans and other living creatures. WHO (2019) defines biological hazards as follows “Biological threats are organic in origin or carried by biological vectors, such as pathogenic germs, poisons, and bioactive compounds. for example, bacteria, viruses, parasites, poisonous wild animals and insects, toxic plants, and pathogen-carrying mosquitoes.”⁽¹⁶⁾ (Aveni, 2020)

Biological hazards, additionally called biohazards, talk to organic materials that pose a hazard to the health of living organisms, in the main that of humans^(16, 17).

This can consist of clinical waste or samples of microorganisms, viruses, or toxins (from an organic source) that could affect human health ⁽¹⁷⁾. (Shroder, 2015). Biological hazards are natural materials that consist of pathogens, infections, crevices, and biodynamic materials ⁽¹⁸⁾ (El-Mohamady et al., 2018.) Occupational biohazards are infectious agents or risky organic substances that exert dangerous results on workers' health, both directly via contamination or not directly via harm to the operating environment, and they, also, can consist of clinical waste, or samples of microorganisms, viruses, or toxins from an organic source ⁽¹⁹⁾ (Rim & Lim, 2014). Biohazards; consist of infections, parasitism, and poisonous and hypersensitive reactions to plant and animal substances. Infections can be due to bacteria, viruses, or fungi. While parasitism may contain protozoa, helminths, or arthropods. Biological hazards had been, also, described to consist of cuts/wounds/lacerations, sharp associated injuries, direct touch with infected specimens/biohazardous materials, bioterrorism, blood-borne pathogens, infectious diseases/infections, airborne diseases, vector-borne diseases, and cross contamination from dirty materials ⁽⁶⁾ (Ndejjo et al., 2015)

2.3.2 Sources of biological hazards

There are many sources that biological hazards come from, such as microorganisms (bacteria, viruses, parasites, fungi), arthropods, trees, birds, animals, and people. These sources can cause different health hazards ranging from dermal itching and allergies to diseases (e.g., tuberculosis, AIDS), malignant neoplasms, and so on ⁽¹⁹⁾ (Rim & Lim, 2014). HCWs are exposed to these biological hazards, mostly; via contact with the patient's bodily materials, such as blood and other body fluids, tissues, mucous, pee, and stools, because these materials have an extreme danger of containing viral or bacterial pathogens ⁽¹¹⁶⁾ (Aveni, 2020).

2.3.3 Modes of Transmission:

Several classes of pathogenic agents, including bacteria, viruses, fungi, parasites, and prions, can cause infection. And the way of spreading depends on the kind of pathogen. Some of the pathogens can communicate through; more than one route; some transmit directly from person to person or through indirect contact, others through blood and other body fluids (bloodborne route), and others by droplet or airborne routes. ⁽¹⁹⁾ (Rim & Lim, 2014). In healthcare facilities, the important paths for the spreading of contagious diseases are bloodborne route, droplet/airborne routes, orofecal route, and contact route ⁽⁴⁾ (Sacadura-Leite et al., 2018)

2.3.4 Portals of entries:

Portal entries of contagious diseases are; *percutaneous*, *mucous membrane* (mouth “ingestion”, eye, nose, vagina, or rectum), *respiratory (inhalation)*, and *skin*. The danger of contagion for an exposed healthcare worker relies on •- the doorway (portal) of exposure, •- the condensing of the infectious agent in the contagious material, •- the virulence of the pathogen, •- the amount of contagious material, and •- the immune status of the exposed person.

percutaneous exposures have the greatest risk of communicating bloodborne infections. Most percutaneous injuries are due to NSIs and sharp instrument accidents. Venipuncture, opening IV lines, handling operating equipment, suturing, and injecting medications put HCWs in danger.

Mucosal exposures arise from spots, bspatters, or a sprinkling of blood; and bodily fluids. Activities related to mucosal exposure hazards include wound care (hemostatic, inspection, lavage, wound debridement), airway aspiration, placement of a nasogastric tube or feeding tube, intubation, and dealing with test samples.

Respiratory exposures caused by the sniffing of airborne or droplets contaminated matters. The danger of exposure increases when a person is close to a patient who spits; coughs; or sneezes for a long time; or is in a badly ventilated room.

Dermal exposure includes dermal contact with infected persons, surrounding surfaces, or materials contaminated with contagious agents. The threat of disease rises when HCW comes into contact with a wide surface area or when the dermis does not adhere (abraded, cracked, or scratched) ⁽²⁰⁾. (Pacella, 2016)

2.3.5 Classification of Biological Hazards:

Biological hazards are classified in several ways; World Health Organization (WHO) classified biological hazards into ten categories in 2019, another time, the WHO divided biological hazards into four groups or categories looking at the risks of microorganisms; to the health of laboratory workers and the community; The United Nations classified biological hazards into several categories under the system of loading hazardous materials.

2.3.5.1 WHO Classification of Biohazards:

In the Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Framework held in GINEVA 2019, WHO classified biological hazards into these ten categories:

- 1- Airborne diseases.
- 2- Waterborne diseases.
- 3- Vector-borne diseases.
- 4- Foodborne outbreaks.
- 5- Insect infestation
- grasshopper

- locust.
- 6- Animal diseases.
- 7- Plant diseases.
- 8- Aeroallergens.
- 9- Antimicrobial resistant microorganisms.
- 10- Animal-human contact
 - Venomous ⁽²¹⁾ (WHO, 2019a)

2.3.5.2 Classification of biological hazards according to their risk level:

The World Health Organization (WHO) classified microorganisms into four groups according to the risk they pose to laboratory workers and the community: *Risk Group 1 (RG1) biological agents*: These include microorganisms unexpected to produce infection in humans; *RG2 biological agents* include; those that can produce illness in people and present a risk to staff, with a low likelihood of transmitting to them or the population, also, the population has access to prevention and effectual medication; *RG3 biological agents*: include those that can produce dangerous diseases to people, pose a significant hazard to staff, and are at risk of disseminating to the population, but effectual medication or prevention is available; Finally, *RG4 biological agents*: include those that can produce acute man disease and pose a high risk to staff with a probability of disseminating to the population, and, in general, there is no effectual prevention or medication for it ⁽²²⁾ (Coelho & Díez, 2015).

However, there are other classifications of biological hazards for regional or national, according to their national policies: these include;

In the USA, the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) classifies pathogens according to their grade of a biological hazard:

Level 1 Biohazard: Bacteria and viruses not so dangerous to the health of humans, including *Bacillus subtilis*, canine hepatitis, *Escherichia coli*, and varicella, as well as some non-infectious bacteria and cell cultures; At this level, preventions contra to these agents are the lowest and may include hand gloves and some kinds of the face shield.

Level 2 Biohazard: Bacteria and viruses that cause only low-grade sickness in people or are hard to be infected in the laboratory by aerosols, e.g., HAV, HBV, HCV, influenza A (some strains), human respiratory syncytial virus, Lyme borreliosis, salmonella, mumps, rubeola(measles), Rida(scrapie), dengue, and HIV; Regular diagnostic tasks on patient samples can be without danger accomplished at Biosafety Level 2 (BSL-2), utilizing BSL-2 practices and procedures(P2); Academic studies (e.g., coculture, viral multiplication research, or dealing with concentrated viruses) can be conducted at BSL-2 (P2), utilizing BSL -3 (P2).

Biohazard Level 3: Bacteria and viruses that can produce Serious or deadly diseases in people, but there are vaccines or other medications for them, e.g., Anthrax, West Nile virus, Equine encephalitis virus, SARS coronavirus, MERS coronavirus, SARS -CoV-2, influenza A H5N1, hantavirus, TB, typhoid, Rift Valley fever, Rocky Mountain spotted fever, yellow fever, and malaria.

Biohazard Level 4: Viruses that cause Serious or deadly sickness in people and there is no vaccine or medication available for it, e.g., Bolivian hemorrhagic fever, Marburg virus, Ebola virus, Lassa, Crimean-Congo hemorrhagic fever, and other hemorrhagic sicknesses, e.g., Nipah virus.

The Variola virus (smallpox) can be included in this group (BSL-4), but for the sake of vaccine, it has been eradicated globally⁽¹⁶⁾ (Aveni, 2020)

In the EU: 'Biological materials' are categorized into four hazard groups based on their grade hazard infection:

Group 1 biological materials are those that possibly do not produce illness in humans:

Group-2 biological materials are those that possibly make sickness in people, -may pose a threat to staff, -possibly not disseminate into the population, and -there is efficacious prevention or medication for them;

Group 3 biological materials are those that possibly produce serious human sicknesses and pose a dangerous risk to the staff, and may pose a threat to disseminate in the population, but effectual prevention or medication is usually available;

Group 4 biological materials are those that produce dangerous human sickness and pose a dangerous risk to the staff and can pose a high risk to disseminate in the population; however, there is no mostly effectual prevention or medication ⁽²³⁾. (Carvalhais et al., 2021)

In Canada: pathogenic agents are also classified into four risk groups; This classification addresses what makes microbes dangerous to the health of an individual or population of humans and/or animals; Those include; • its natural occurrence in the vicinity; • Its capability to produce illness; • The seriousness of the illness; • Probability of dissemination within a group (e.g., from one individual to another); • The obtainability of effectual prophylaxis for disease (e.g., vaccinations); and • The obtainability of an efficacious drug to cure the illness (e.g., antibiotics). The four risk groups are:

- 1- RG-1; Have no or low personal threat, and low population threat.
- 2- RG2; Have a moderate personal threat, and low population threat
- 3- RG3; Have a high personal threat and low population threat.
- 4- RG4; Have a high personal threat and high population threat. ⁽²⁴⁾ (CBG, 2020)

In Australia: The Australian Standard for Microbiological Safety and Containment has classified pathogenic microorganisms for humans into four hazard groups as follows:

- 1- Risk Group 1 (RG1), such as microorganisms that probably do not produce human or zoonotic infection in fit grown-up persons. Microbiological Safety and containment did not mention this class of microorganisms because of their large number. But in Australian schools, these germs are named as examples; *Bacillus subtilis*, *Escherichia coli* (K-12), *Micrococcus luteus*, *Penicillium chrysogenum*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, and *Staphylococcus epidermidis*.
- 2- RG-2 include germs that may not cause a significant danger to laboratory staff, populations, domestic animals, or the environment. Lab exposures of these germs can produce disease, but there are efficacious medications and prophylaxis controls, and the danger of dissemination is limited. This class of germs includes *Bordetella pertussis*, *Chlamydia* spp., and *Vibrio cholerae*.
- 3- RG3 includes germs that generally produce severe illness in humans or animals and can pose a serious hazard to laboratory staff. They can pose a low to moderate danger if they disseminate into the population or the environment, but prophylaxis controls or efficacious medications are mainly obtainable. These germs include *Bacillus anthracis*, *Coxiella burnetii*, and *Yersinia pestis*.
- 4- RG4 includes microbes that mainly cause fatal sickness to people or animals, pose a dangerous threat to lab staff, and are easily communicated from person to person. And there are no Efficacious medications and prophylaxis controls. These germs include the Ebola virus and the Lassa virus. ⁽²⁵⁾ (ASTA, 2017).

In Ireland, Biological materials are classified (according to the Code of Practice to the Safety, Health, and Welfare at Work Regulations 2013 and 2020, for biological microorganisms) into risk groups 1 (RG-1) – RG2, RG3, and RG4. According to the classification system, group 1 substances are the least dangerous, while group four substances are the riskiest. The grouping system is based on: whether the microbe is infectious to the people, - The microbe is a danger to HCWs, - The agent is spreadable to the population, - Efficacious medication or prevention is obtainable⁽²⁶⁾ (HSA, 2020).

In China: The “Pathogenic microbiology laboratory biosafety regulations” divided pathogenic microorganisms into four groups, with group 1 demonstrated as the most dangerous, in contrast to the WHO, NIH, the EU, and others, which clarified group 4 as the most hazardous⁽²⁷⁾ (Tian & Zheng, 2014)

2.3.5.3 Classification of biological hazards by UN numbers:

Biologically hazards are classified using the United Nations (UN) *classification system for the carriage of dangerous goods*. Dangerous goods are assigned internationally agreed UN class numbers which are:

*Class 1: Explosives *Class 2: Gases *Class 3: Flammable liquids *Class 4: Flammable solids *Class 5: Oxidizing substances *Class 6: Toxic substances (6.1 Toxic substance or 6.2 Infectious substance) *Class 7: Radioactive substances *Class 8: Corrosive substances *Class 9: Miscellaneous dangerous goods.

The UN classification of Biological Hazards (Infectious materials) is UN sub-class 6.2 pathogenic materials under the class-6 group. Biological hazards are classified, by UN numbers, into the following categories for the carriage of dangerous goods.

- 1- Category A: Pathogenic agents that can lead to persistent disability, deadly illness, or death in exposed people or both people and animals. For example,

Bacillus anthracis (culture only), Brucella spp (culture only), Clostridium botulinum (culture only), Crimean-Congo hemorrhagic fever, Dengue virus (culture only), Hepatitis B virus (culture only), HIV (culture only), Lassa virus, Marburg virus, Monkeypox virus, Mycobacterium tuberculosis (culture only), Yersinia pestis (culture only), etc. This category is specified in UN 2814.

- 2- Category A: Pathogenic agents that can produce persistent disability, deadly illness, or death in exposed animals only, for example, African swine fever virus (culture only), Classical swine fever virus (culture only), Foot and mouth disease virus (culture only), Sheep-pox virus (culture only), Goat-pox virus (culture only), Vesicular stomatitis virus (culture only), specified to UN 2900.
- 3- Category B: Pathogenic materials that cannot produce persistent disability, deadly illness, or death in exposed people or animals, specified to UN 3373
- 4- Exempt materials: for example, non-infectious germs to both animals and people, materials with neutralized or inactivated infectious germs, environmental specimens like food and drink which are not bearing potential hazard of infection, dried blood spots, fecal occult blood samples, blood, and blood products prepared for transfusion, tissues, and organs intended for transplantation, human, and animal samples in which there is a low probability of the presence of infectious agents.
- 5- Genetically modified organisms (GMOs); are not contagious to humans or animals but may harm animals, trees, or other microorganisms in a way that does not occur naturally, assigned to UN 3245.
- 6- Medical or clinical wastes containing group A infectious substances generated from the medical treatment of humans or animals shall be assigned to UN 2814, UN 2900, or UN 3549 as appropriate. The medical or clinical wastes which are reasonably believed to have a low probability of

containing infectious substances shall be assigned to UN 3291. ⁽²⁸⁾ (UN, 2019)

2.3.5.4 Classification of Biohazards in an Account of Occupations:

Biological hazards can be classified into six categories according to the associations between occupations and biohazards (infections):

- 1- Contact with diseased living animals;
- 2- Contact with infected animal products;
- 3- Insect bites (e.g., Ticks, Flea, or Mite)
- 4- Contact with human or animal excreta
- 5- Contact with a diseased patient or blood;
- 6- And raising dust containing infectious agents ^(19, 29) (Rim & Lim, 2014), (Haz-Map, 2018)

2.4 Common biohazards that expose to HCWs:

HCWs are exposed to a variety of occupational hazards including biological, chemical, physical, radiological, ergonomic, and psychosocial hazards, however, the major hazard faced by the HCWs are biological hazards. According to the WHO, the most common occupational infections of worry in the health field are tuberculosis, hepatitis B, hepatitis C, HIV/AIDS, and respiratory infections especially coronaviruses and influenza ⁽³⁰⁾ (Senthil et al., 2015) and (WHO)⁽³⁰⁾.

Exposure to biological hazards, for example, hepatitis B virus (HBV), HIV, influenza, and tuberculosis (TB) in health facilities have gained more attention concerning interventions, including safety programs, personal protective equipment (PPE), and research work ⁽³¹⁾ (Tawiah et al., 2022)., Healthcare workers

are at increased risk for skin-infectious agents such as scabies or herpes simplex virus 1/2 and antimicrobial-resistant organisms (e.g., methicillin/oxacillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA), vancomycin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (VRSA)), exposure when they take care of their patients. These pathogens are transmitted by contact and often infect healthcare workers. Antibiotic-resistant organisms are one of the most serious health threats to patients and healthcare workers, particularly when patients are cured with broad-spectrum antibiotics for long periods and when they are highly vulnerable to infection. MRSA is a recurring problem in European hospitals and is transmitted by direct contact or through droplets. ⁽⁴⁾ (Sacadura-Leite et al., 2018)

Healthcare workers are routinely exposed to other than infectious agents, Chemicals used in healthcare settings such as ethylene oxide, formaldehyde, and antineoplastic medications, cleaning and disinfecting agents, and latex. These agents are linked to causing Asthma, Negative Reproductive Outcomes, and cancers ^(31, 32) (Tawiah et al., 2022) (Rai et al., 2021)

2.4.1 Bloodborne infections:

The blood-borne infections that most commonly affect HCWs in health settings are Hepatitis B (HBV), Hepatitis C (HCV), and Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) infections ^(33, 34, 35) (Gorman et al., 2014). (Abuduxike et al., 2021) (Sheikh et al., 2021). They mostly affect HCWs who are exposed to blood and other body fluids via sharps or needlestick injuries (NSIs) when they are at work for caring patients ^(34, 35) (Abuduxike et al., 2021) (Sheikh et al., 2021). Besides those infections: there are other blood-borne viral diseases exposed to HCWs, especially When they are handling contaminated needles or surgical instruments ⁽¹⁹⁾ (Rim & Lim, 2014). There are more than 20 blood-borne pathogens that can transmit by Needle stick injuries (NSIs), including HIV, hepatitis B virus (HBV), hepatitis C

virus (HCV), human T cell leukemia virus, Ebola, and seldom cases, malaria. ⁽³⁶⁾ (Anderton, 2019)

Blood-borne infections affect all health workers around the world. But they pose the highest risk to those in developing countries, especially, those in Sub-Saharan Africa, which are repeatedly affected by biological hazards. ⁽⁶⁾ (Ndejjo et al., 2015).

2.4.2 Droplet/airborne infections:

Healthcare workers are at high risk of many droplet/airborne pathogens infections, but the most common respiratory infections among healthcare workers during this period are; COVID-19, Influenza, and TB ⁽³⁰⁾ (WHO). Dissemination of tuberculosis, caused by *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, is a significant hazard for patients and healthcare workers. Invisible droplets (or droplet nuclei) are formed when respiratory tuberculosis patients cough, sneeze, and speak and can remain airborne and caught in air currents for a long time. Healthcare workers are at greater risk when doing certain procedures that involve growing exposure to tracheobronchial secretions, such as; autopsy, bronchoscopy, extubating/intubation, oral hygiene, secretion aspiration, sputum examination, and sputum induction ⁽⁴⁾ (Sacadura-Leite et al., 2018). The risk of contracting tuberculosis depends on the condition of the clinic, its prevalence in the community, and the exposure of medical staff. The annual rate of tuberculosis infection (ARTI) in healthcare workers ranges from 0.1% to 2% in unexposed healthcare workers, compared to 1-10% in greatly exposed healthcare workers. The proportion of healthcare workers with latent tuberculosis infection (LTBI) is 20% in developed countries, 40% in Russia, and 70% in third-world countries. The LTBI average among health workers in developing countries was 54% (33% to 79%), while ARTI ranged from 0.5 to 14%. LTBI is more common in healthcare workers than in the general population. ARTIs in healthcare workers occurred between 60 to 5,780 per 100,000 compared to an annual occurrence of 25 to 5,361 per 100,000 in the general

population. In a study from South Africa, the greater range of healthcare workers affected with TB was in the internal medicine, pediatric, and surgical services at the time of diagnosis⁽³³⁾ (Gorman et al., 2014)

Healthcare workers (HCWs) are one of the groups most at risk of contracting and dying from COVID-19.⁽¹³⁾ (Dahie et al., 2022). Amnesty International estimates that 17,000 healthcare workers died from work-related infections in March 2021 during the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic⁽³⁷⁾ (Edgar et al., 2022). Amnesty International has also reported that more than 7,000 healthcare workers worldwide have lost their lives because of COVID-19.⁽³⁸⁾ (Thirunavukkarasu et al., 2021). According to the World Health Organization, more than 10,000 health workers in Africa have been infected with COVID-19, making it a serious threat to the health of healthcare workers in the workplace⁽¹³⁾ (Dahie et al., 2022). Frontline healthcare workers were at least three times more likely to report a positive COVID-19 test than the rest of the population. Healthcare workers working directly with COVID-19 patients or without proper personal protective equipment were most at risk. A systematic living review appraised the dissemination of SARS-CoV-2 infection among healthcare workers in July 2020 at 11% globally, with nurses primarily infected⁽³⁷⁾ (Edgar et al., 2022). The heterogeneity of SARS-CoV-2 and the simplicity of transmission through aerosols, droplets, contact, and indirect contact support wide distribution in healthcare facilities. The hazard of airborne transmission was also talked about. Causative factors for healthcare spreading include unprotected exposure, extended direct contact with a COVID-19 patient, exposure to bodily wastes, and certain events such as aerosol-generating procedures. Appropriate PPE for healthcare workers includes waterproof gowns or gowns with waterproof aprons, eye shields such as face protectors or goggles, and respiratory tract prevention via surgical masks or respirators. Water-resistant surgical masks prevent the spreading of bigger droplets, aerosols, and splashes

to medical staff and protect the patient from medical-staff breathing, just like during an operation. They are loose and disposable; they are not intended to protect healthcare workers from airborne infections ⁽³⁷⁾ (Edgar et al., 2022). The lack of PPE gives rise to the infections and death of healthcare workers and ultimately to the failure and destruction of healthcare systems ⁽³⁷⁾ (Edgar et al., 2022)

Three types of influenza viruses, called influenza A, B, and C, exist, and types A and B are capable of producing seasonal epidemics in people: especially, Influenza A is the most commonly disseminating type and, because it is sensitive to antigenic changes, it is the type most likely to cause dangerous sickness. The course of influenza can be low-grade or severe depending on several factors and circumstances (i.e., age, co-morbidity, immune condition, seasonal flu strain). However, the general burden of influenza is ponderous both in clinical, epidemiological, and societal terms. ⁽³⁹⁾ (Dini et al., 2018). Healthcare workers are more likely to be infected with Influenza than the general population. A systematic review compared the occurrence of influenza in healthy adults and healthcare workers; the prevalence was much higher among healthcare workers. ⁽⁴⁰⁾ (World Health Organization, n.d.) World Health Organization (WHO) has estimated that yearly outbreaks may affect from 5% to 15% of the population globally, inducing up to 4–5 million serious cases and from 250,000 to 500,000 deaths, with a fatality rate of 4–8% among adults hospitalized and greater than 10–15%, during pestilences, and among the immunosuppressed subjects ⁽³⁹⁾ (Dini et al., 2018). After an overall review of 26 studies; and a meta-analysis of 15 trials, Lietz et al. found that influenza incidence was significantly higher in healthcare workers at 6.3% than in healthy working adults (5.1%). During the reported influenza outbreaks, the infection rate among healthcare workers ranged from 18% to 24%, higher than among the whole other population (11%). ⁽²⁹⁾ (Hassan et al., 2022). Another study found that 59% of healthcare workers caring for influenza patients

were infected with the virus during influenza outbreaks in healthcare settings. Those who work in emergency rooms and clinical facilities are most in danger, and of all healthcare workers, nurses are the most vulnerable to the virus ⁽⁴⁰⁾ (World Health Organization, n.d.). Healthcare workers often work during the time they have an influenza-like illness (ILI) (40-83%), increasing the possibility of influenza dissemination to co-workers and patients ⁽⁴¹⁾ (Hassan et al., 2022). So, the WHO suggests that all healthcare workers should be vaccinated against cyclical influenza every autumn. ⁽⁴⁰⁾ (World Health Organization, n.d.)

2.5 Other Biological Hazards:

Besides the pathogens I mentioned above, the HCWs are exposed to many other pathogens transmitted by blood-borne, droplet/airborne, fecal-oral, and dermal (contact) routes. There are more than 20 blood-borne pathogens that can be contagious by Needle stick injuries (NSIs), including HIV, hepatitis B virus (HBV), hepatitis C virus (HCV), human T cell leukemia virus, Ebola, and seldom cases, malaria. ⁽³⁶⁾ (Anderton, 2019).

Healthcare workers are at high risk of droplet/airborne pathogens infections other than; influenza, & tuberculosis, and COVID-19. These include; Adenovirus, arenavirus infection, Crimean-Congo hemorrhagic fever, diphtheria, Ebola-Marburg virus infection, Lassa fever, measles, meningococcus, monkeypox, mumps, Mycoplasma infection, parvovirus infection, pertussis, rubella, SARS, Varicella ⁽¹⁹⁾ (Rim & Lim, 2014). In addition to; Anthrax, Aspergillosis, Blastomycosis, Enteroviruses, Rotavirus, Rhinovirus, Streptococcus pneumoniae, Legionellosis, Smallpox, Cryptococcosis, and Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS). All of these are common droplet/airborne transmitted pathogens. ⁽⁴²⁾ (Ather, 2022).

Respiratory diseases are transmitted through contact with contaminated respiratory secretions with healthcare workers' mucosae (oral, nasal); therefore, the use of a surgical mask can significantly reduce the danger of dissemination. Some of these infections can be prevented by vaccination, for example, Influenza, rubella, measles, mumps, TB, and chickenpox (varicella), and should be considered an occupational hazard. The staff of pediatric wards and those who work with immunosuppressed patients, such as those: Infectious diseases, hematology, oncology, and post-transplant wards, appear to be in increased danger of exposure ⁽⁴⁾ (Sacadura-Leite et al., 2018).

The most dangerous pathogens that can be transmitted to healthcare workers by the fecal-oral route; -Mostly due to HCWs' lack of commitment to the standard precautions especially wearing PPE (gloves) and handwashing; -are *Campylobacter jejuni/coli*, *Clostridium difficile*, enterohemorrhagic *Escherichia coli*, enteropathogenic *Escherichia coli*, rotaviruses, *Salmonella* spp., *Shigella* spp., *Vibrio cholerae*, and *Yersinia enterocolitica*, among others ⁽⁴⁾ (Sacadura-Leite et al., 2018).

Dermal exposure includes skin contact with infected patients (direct contact), surrounding surfaces, or objects contaminated with contagious agents (indirect contact). The danger of contagion increases when the employee comes into contact with a large surface area or when the skin is not intact (abraded, cracked, or scratched). Drug-resistant organisms such as methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* and vancomycin-resistant enterococci constitute an additional threat from skin exposure. Transmission may be associated with contact with diseased patients and the medical devices used on them. ⁽⁴³⁾ (Osman S. Mohammed, 2015). Other pathogens include herpes simplex virus 1 or 2, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Enterobacter* spp., *Enterococcus faecium*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* can also be transmitted by contact but do not mostly;

cause disease in healthy individuals. However, they can potentially cause dangerous health problems, particularly pneumonia or wound infections. ⁽⁴⁾ (Sacadura-Leite et al., 2018) Skin parasites (e.g., scabies, lice, etc.) can also be transmitted through skin contact to healthcare workers. Workplace activities that expose medical personnel include; examining a patient, turning or moving patients, and changing bed lines or wound dressings⁽⁴³⁾ (Osman S. Mohammed, 2015). In addition, medical staff can act as vectors of spread in health facilities, when colonized with these pathogens. These factors are of particular concern in hospitals, especially when they develop resistance to antibiotics. ⁽⁴⁾ (Sacadura-Leite et al., 2018)

2.6 Standard Precautions and preventive measures for HCWs against Biohazards:

Healthcare workers are in constant contact with patients who expose them to infections, so they need proper protective measures to reduce the risk of infection. ⁽⁶⁾ (Ndejjo et al., 2015). Biological hazards generally, and especially common biological hazards among healthcare workers, such as HBV, HCV, HIV, TB, Influenza, and Covid-19 have been given a strong intervening interest, whether it be Safety measures protocols, PPE, and scholars' research studies. ⁽³¹⁾ (Tawiah et al., 2022). But in most sub-Saharan African countries, and particularly in Eastern ones, data on occupational risks in healthcare workers and risk reduction measures are still lacking. Potential victims of both biological and nonbiological hazards typically were not wearing all the necessary personal protective equipment, also Long working hours and job-related stress are potentially increasing the likelihood of exposure to biological hazards. ⁽⁶⁾ (Ndejjo et al., 2015). Not implementing all protective precautions in health settings is the main reason why occupational biohazards are so many in poor countries. The problem of occupational injuries and exposure in the healthcare sector poses a threat to both developed and developing

countries. However, in developed countries, there are significant reductions in exposure frequency and improvements in exposure reduction, compared to developing countries where occupational health and safety are not a priority. In addition to inadequate data collection systems, inadequate enforcement of safety rules and regulations, neglect of guidelines, and non-compliance with standard precautions by healthcare professionals, a lack of data and inadequate implementation of guidelines are among the top reasons why workplace health and safety have received little attention in third-world countries. ⁽³¹⁾ (Tawiah et al., 2022)

Healthcare workers are at risk for many diseases when they are caring the patients, especially, viral and bacterial infections such as bloodborne, droplet/airborne, fecal-oral, and dermal infections; therefore, the standard precautions needed are 1- personal protective equipment (gloves, masks, glasses,), 2- appropriate hygienic measures (hand washing, respiratory hygiene, environmental hygiene), 3- safe collection and disposal of health-care waste (infectious specimens, needle/sharps waste, contaminated linen), and safe handling and cleaning of blood spills and other body fluids. In the laboratories, to avoid infections and allergies caused by handling microorganisms and cell cultures, especially of human tissues; accidental spills, and needlestick injuries, these precautions should be taken; Microbiological safety cabinets, dust and aerosol reducing measures, safe handling and transport of samples, appropriate personal protection and hygiene measures, decontamination and emergency measures for spills, restricted access, biosafety label ⁽¹⁹⁾ (Rim & Lim, 2014). Administrative controls to manage biological hazards are also important such as; Education and training of HCWs, adequate supervision, emergency procedures, monitoring exposure, and immunizations. WHO recommendations on health workers' vaccinations include Bacillus Calmette–Guérin (BCG), hepatitis B, polio, pertussis, diphtheria, measles, rubella,

meningococcal, influenza, varicella, COVID-19 and cholera ⁽³⁰⁾ (WHO, Occupational infections).

2.6.2 Standard control of bloodborne pathogens:

All patients' blood and body fluids should be handled as infectious, whether or not the infection has been proven. These practices are referred to as standard precautions. They include hand washing, wearing PPE, injection safety, safe dealing with potentially contaminated devices or materials, and respiratory/cough hygiene. Where possible, needle-free systems should replace sharp instruments. Reduce injections and discard unnecessary sharps instruments such as Towel clamps used in surgery. Replace the following items whenever attainable: hollow needles, needle equipment that must be disassembled by the healthcare worker; remaining needles exposed after using a syringe; and tube-attached needles such as Butterflies, which are difficult to put in sharps containers. The ideal sharp devices with technical sharps protection are "passive ones" that have built-in security that doesn't require user activation, unlike active instruments that the user can easily activate. When using a passive instrument there is a clear decrease in NSIs (0.06 NSI/10,000 devices used) compared to the active instruments (5.2 NSI / 10,000 devices used). Infusion treatment and vascular access: needleless or shielded intravenous needle systems reduce NSIs associated with IV connectors by 62-88%. Needle-free systems are available for administering therapies and fluids through the catheter port with needleless connections. Also, jet injection systems are available that deliver drugs under the skin or through the muscles. Needleless blunt-entry intravenous administration sets, safety-locking butterfly needles, and non-slip disposable safety syringes are other examples of designed controls. If the use of a needle is necessary, it must be able to retract, sheathe, or blunt immediately after use ⁽³³⁾ (Gorman et al., 2014).

Syringes: use syringes with acupuncture protection features such as those in which the needle pulls back after use or those that have a shield covering the needles used. It is strictly forbidden to reassemble used needles and must be transferred into sharps containers after use or destroyed using an electrical device fabricated for this aim. When collecting blood; venipuncture injuries can be decreased by needle caps (by 82%), self-locking needles (by 76%), hinged needle covers (by 66%), sliding caps, and scalp vein needles (butterfly-type) (by 23%). (Gorman et al., 2014)

Suture needles: un-sharped-tip suture needles decrease the danger of NSI by 69%, and are also preferred to decrease percutaneous incidences. They are most commonly used to suture less-thickness tissues like the face and muscles, where over 50% of NSI sutures occur. Skin, blood vessels, and intestines are mostly used with sharp sewing needles, but no-sew techniques also exist. Sharps Containers should be found in all areas where sharps are present. They should be resealable, resistant to puncture, leakage, and spillage, contamination-free, and replaced when one-quarter were remaining. It should be easy to know when they are full. They should be placed no more than 54 inches off the ground for easy access. When it is not wall mounted, it should be near to work area to avoid injury when handling objects. PPE, including Gloves, gowns, eye protection (such as goggles or glasses with solid side shields), and face shields must be supplied to the HCWs, in proper sizes and numbers, and for free. Wearing of PPE must be compulsory, depending on the exposed area. Where sharp tools are necessary, labor practices controls should be followed, including using tools instead of fingers to hold needles, oral guidance while passing sharps, do not transfer by hand, using a specific area in which to place them, reducing splashing or splattering, and double gloves. Healthcare workers should be educated about the threats of blood-borne pathogens during the first time of work and annually. All HCWs should be offered the HBV vaccine. In the event of exposure, the HCW should have immediate access to

physicians because HIV postexposure prophylaxis is best effective within two hours of exposure. HBV postexposure prophylaxis is best effective within 24 hours⁽³³⁾ (Gorman et al., 2014).

2.6.3 Standard control of droplet/airborne pathogens:

Administrative measures are essential to decrease the danger of exposure for people with suspected or proven tuberculosis or other airborne diseases. These measures include a written plan to limit infection, rapid identification and segregation of suspected cases, training of HCWs, immediate reporting of diagnostic tests, patient education, and elevating public awareness.

Routine tuberculin skin testing (TST) should be performed by the healthcare worker and those with positive reactions should be screened for TB. Environmental controls are also essential for the protection against airborne infections. These controls include Local exhaust ventilation (LEV), general ventilation (both natural and mechanical), or room air purifiers (filters or ultraviolet germicidal (UVGI) radiation). General Ventilation systems prevent the incidence of infection by diluting and eradicating pathogens. Respirators are the last line of protection and are used where the risk of exposure is continuous. It requires yearly fit checking to ensure HCWs are using adequately sized respirators. Reducing respirator-seal leakage is necessary to provide appropriate prevention. Where healthcare workers may be exposed to the transmission of airborne pathogens, the CDC and others recommend the use of N95 respirators or better-quality respirators. The CDC now recommends N95 or better respirators for those exposed to patients with suspected or diagnosed tuberculosis. The WHO also issued a strong recommendation on the utilization of particulate respirators in healthcare settings in its 2009 guidance on combating TB infection. WHO recommends the use of respirators that fulfill or surpass the NIOSH standard N95 or FFP2 (filtering facepiece with a medium grade of protection) and are CE recognized (i.e., conform to European Union directives),

particularly during times of procedures that create a high aerosol risk associated with high-risk of TB transmission (e.g., bronchoscopy, intubation, sputum induction procedures, airway suction, and autopsy, or pulmonary surgery using high-speed equipment) and in the care of infected patients with multidrug-resistant tuberculosis (MDR-TB) and tuberculosis with extensive drug resistance (XDR-TB) or suspected infected to MDR -TB or XDR-TB. ⁽³³⁾ (Gorman et al., 2014)

2.6.1 Importance of PPEs for reducing biohazards:

Some studies have demonstrated that the use of all necessary personal protective equipment has been associated with reduced exposure to biological and non-biological hazards. Wearing of PPEs and compliance with the utilization of it has long been accepted as essential infection preventive measures in healthcare facilities which should be emphasized to decrease exposure to biological and other work-related hazards. ⁽⁵⁾ (Ndejjo et al., 2015). While inadequate personal protective measures related significantly to a higher risk of biological and non-biological health hazards ⁽³⁸⁾ (Thirunavukkarasu et al., 2021).

PPE should be custom-fit to provide adequate protection against specific biological agents or hazards. Potential routes of exposure to biological agents and hazards should be considered when selecting appropriate PPE. All PPE must be carefully selected and properly maintained, serviced, and cleaned. Workers must be fully trained in its use and limitations. To make PPE effective, there must be a procedure for selection, use, inspection, cleaning, maintenance, storage, useful life, and disposal of PPE. It must be free and suitable for all HCWs. PPE include; gloves, safety glasses, respirators, face protectors, medical mask, coats, gowns, aprons, coveralls, hair and shoe covers, and air-line respirators ⁽⁴⁴⁾ (Geneva, 20-24 June 2022)

And in the end, WHO has developed a guideline that has proven minimal and full requirements for infection protection and control, which is sufficient for the safety of health workers if hospitals applied properly.

The minimal requirement for infection protection and control:

The minimum guidelines cover these topics:

- hand washing.
- Decontamination of medical equipment and care items.
- environmental sanitation.
- the management of medical waste.
- Transmission Precautions.
- safe injection.
- Protection of medical staff.
- Medical asepsis.
- Assessment of the injured person's state of health (triage).
- And the development and Achievement of a strategy for training and publicizing the IPC guidelines. ⁽⁴⁹⁾

(WHO, 2019)

Fully requirements for infection protection and control:

1- standard precautions: [

- Hand washing.
- Wearing of PPE.
- Decontamination and Sterilization of medical equipment.
- Safe dealing with dirty linen and clothes.
- Appropriate handling of medical waste.
- Positioning of patients.
- Respiratory and cough hygiene.
- Environmental sanitation.
- Safe injection practices.
- Protection, safety, and post-exposure prevention of healthcare workers].

2- transmission-based precautions (Contact, droplet, airborne);

3- Medical asepsis and equipment management for medical procedures;

4- specific guidelines for the prevention of the most common healthcare-associated infections (HAIs) (e.g., catheter-related urinary tract infections, postoperative wound infections, central catheter-related circulatory infections, mechanically ventilated pneumonia), depending on the context and complexity of the "assistance". ⁽⁴⁹⁾ (WHO, 2019)

2.7 PEP plan after exposure to HBV, HCV, and HIV:

As soon as the infection develops post-exposure prophylaxis health plan should be made for a health worker 24 hours a day, which is a rapid clinical assessment, hazard analysis, advising, therapy and prophylaxis, and follow-up to the sort and source of the exposure. Percutaneous injury and mucous membrane contact with infected human blood, seeable-blood containing liquids, tissue, and other infectious substances such as; semen, vaginal discharges, CSF, synovial, pleural, peritoneal, pericardial, and amniotic fluids can communicate bloodborne pathogens. Skin contact with these matters does not pose the risk of transmission unless the skin is open (abraded, cracked, excoriated, open cut).

If a healthcare worker is exposed to blood or body fluids, overflow the exposed-mucous membranes with plenty of water, wash the wound, and skin with soap and water, and do not use bleaches, decontaminants, or germicidal agents directly to the injuries. Do a quick medical assessment, and get the history of exposure circumstances, source patient (HBsAg, HCV & HIV antibody existence), and vaccination history of exposed HCW (HB vaccine & vaccine response status, and HBV, HCV, HIV immune situation), by assessing the possibility of passing HBV, HCV, and HIV, based on the kind and volume of body materials (blood, observable-blood containing fluid, other possibly contagious fluid or tissue), and the route of transmission (percutaneous injury, mucous membrane, open skin, bites resulting in blood exposure). Take blood samples both from the patient and health worker for laboratory analysis. Decide the potential need for the tetanus vaccine, hepatitis B PEP, HIV PEP, and the dosage of the drugs as soon as possible. Advice should be given to exposed health workers concerning the risk of the bloodborne pathogen, explaining the side effects and the benefits of the obtainable medicines. Evaluate the dosage and side effects of the prescribed medication.

Make as soon as possible HB, HC, and HIV tests on the exposure source. Perform a rapid HIV antibody, because direct viral assay (HIV p24 antigen enzyme immunoassay, HIV RNA, HCV RNA) is not preferred. Also, testing of contaminated instruments (needles and sharps) is not preferred. If the HIV test is positive get CD4+ T-Cell count, viral load, existing and prior antiretroviral treatment, and history of antiretroviral resistance and prediction, to help prescription to appropriate PEP. If this information is not available, do not hesitate to start PEP, as medication changes can be made on follow-up within 72 hours after the incident.

If the source patient becomes negative for blood-borne infections, it is not required to make testing or follow-up for exposed HCW. If a patient's condition is not known (e.g., not accepted such a diagnosis), evaluate medical symptoms, clinical diagnosis, and the history of hazardous behaviors. If the source is completely unknown, assess whether the source is at high risk for infection and the possibility of infection among the patients in that setting.

Any unvaccinated medical staff exposed to blood or body fluids of HBsAg positive should be given the HB vaccine series. ⁽²⁰⁾ (Pacella, 2016). Postexposure prophylaxis of HBV is highly effective in the first 24 hours ⁽³³⁾ ((Gorman et al., 2014). If HB immunoglobulin (HBIG) is prescribed, it should be given within 24 hours because its efficacy after seven days is unknown. If the exposed HCW is unvaccinated or nonimmune and the source is positive, give HBIGx1 and HB vaccine series. If the source is negative, unknown, or the HBsAg test is not available, just give the vaccine series. If the exposed person is priorly vaccinated, with enough level of serum antibody, no treatment or follow-up is needed. If the antibody level is insufficient and the source is positive or known high risk, give HBIGx1 and vaccine or HBIGx2. The immunoglobulin dose is 0.06ml/kg IM.

If the source patient is HCV-positive, examine the exposed HCW anti-HCV and alanine aminotransferase (ALT) at baseline and follow up at 4 to 6 months. After exposure, a month to a month and a half, make HCV RNA analysis if needed. After exposure to HCV-positive blood, no immunoglobulin or antiviral drugs are prescribed as PEP. During the follow-up, those exposed to HBV and HCV-positive blood do not need any preventive measures to avoid further transmission, however, they must avoid donating blood, plasma, organs, tissue, or semen.

Factors influencing managing HIV exposure include the kind of exposure (transdermal, mucosa layers, or dermal), amount of exposure (little or large), and HIV condition of the source. If the source person is negative, no examination or follow-up is needed. But if the source is HIV positive or suspected to have acute retroviral syndrome begin the appropriate PEP and follow-up checking as soon as possible, ⁽²⁰⁾ (Pacella, 2016) as HIV postexposure prophylaxis has a maximum efficacy within two hours of exposure ⁽³³⁾ (Gorman et al., 2014). because starting PEP after 24 to 36 hours from exposure is less effective. Nevertheless, give a PEP even if the interval exceeds 36 hours. The PEP should contain three or more tolerable antiretroviral drugs. The appropriate HIV PEP drugs are; Raltegravir (400mgx1x2) + Truvada (Tenofovir DF300mg+emtricitabine 200mg twice daily). There are many alternative drugs, for example, a combination of [Elvitegravir, cobicistat, tenofovir DF + emtricitabine (Stribild)]. The excellent duration of PEP is unknown, but the US CDC recommends four weeks of treatment. The exposed HCW must avoid secondary transmission during the first 6 to 12 weeks. The follow-up testing consists of; an HIV examination initially, at 6 weeks, at 12 weeks, and at 6 months. ⁽²⁰⁾ (Pacella, 2016.)

2.8 PEP plan after exposure to TB, Influenza, and COVID-19:

Nearly 20% of exposed individuals to TB become infected. So, CDC advised preventive therapy after exposure. The vaccine for TB is BCG and recommended

to healthcare workers by WHO and all countries except in the USA. ⁽²⁰⁾ (Pacella, 2016). For persons with affirmed MTB exposure, a risk classification system should be established based on the stake of infection post-exposure, the danger of progressing illness from infection, and the danger of spreading after sickness onset. For high-risk individuals, PEP can be performed regardless of tuberculosis test results. For intermediate-risk individuals, those who test positive for TB infection should be given preference for preventive treatment. On the other hand, regular assessments and follow-up visits can be suggested for people at low stakes. Currently, chemoprevention is the most usual PEP tool for tuberculosis. Although the effectiveness of TB prophylaxis therapies accessible now is good (ranging from 60% to 90%), it must not be ignored side effects and drug incompatibilities. ⁽⁴⁵⁾ (Xin et al., 2021). WHO nowadays printed practical guidance for tuberculosis prophylaxis therapy toward national control strategies. This document emphasizes the necessity of averting active tuberculosis and recommends shorter TBI medications, e.g., rifapentine (P, RPT) and isoniazid (H, INH) weekly for 3 months (3HP) or RPT and INH daily for 1 a month. ⁽⁴⁶⁾ (Heffernan et al., 2022).

Influenza has a vaccine, recommended once yearly. For exposed persons not vaccinated within the past year, the vaccine will not prevent them from the disease but is not dangerous and may safeguard them in case of future exposure. Prescribe oseltamivir or zanamivir as PEP for healthcare workers who have high-risk exposure to influenza. ⁽²⁰⁾ (Pacella, 2016).

In March and May 2020, the Indian Council for Medical Research (ICMR) approved Hydroxychloroquine sulfate (HCQ) as PEP for people at stakes for SARS-CoV-2 contagion, like all asymptomatic healthcare workers (HCWs) who treated patients with or suspected COVID-19, and all asymptomatic individuals live with the lab-diagnosed patient. However, there is conflicting scientific evidence supporting or refuting the effectiveness of HCQ as a PEP to prevent COVID-19 in

people at stakes of SARS-CoV-2 contagion. According to Boulware et al., research result, HCQ was not suitable as a post-exposure prophylaxis (PEP) for protection against COVID-19, but most of the respondents were HCWs. At the same time, other published research has supported HCQ prophylaxis as a possible prophylaxis or curative procedure against COVID-19. Finally, research by Dhibar and colleagues concluded that PEP with HCQ does not help prevent COVID-19 in asymptomatic persons who have close contact with laboratory-confirmed COVID-19 patients. So, pre-exposure protective measures are the best tools for protection against COVID-19, these measures include; mass vaccinations, public awareness, mask use, social distancing, and personal hygiene. ⁽⁴⁷⁾ (Dhibar et al., 2023).

2.9 Methodology:

Biological hazards especially infections are among the most important risks for healthcare workers. There are regulations made to reduce exposure to biological hazards, such as standard precautions especially, PPE and handwashing. Even so, some healthcare workers in developing countries are unaware of exposures and do not wear all necessary protective equipment, so they are vulnerable to biological hazards; even if they are aware of potential biological hazards, personal protective equipment (PPEs) and other safety devices to reduce biological hazards may not be available. In Somalia, there is a problem related to the risk of a biological hazard in all hospitals because there is a lack or shortage of personal protective equipment, a lack of proper sanitation, and a lack of proper medical waste disposal management. This study was conducted through a descriptive cross-sectional survey research design to demonstrate the biological hazards among healthcare workers, as biological hazards are the most occupational concern in health settings. The study area is Garowe general hospital (GGH), located in Garowe, The capital city of Puntland State, Somalia. The objectives of the research are: To investigate or determine the common biological hazards among health workers in Garowe

General Hospital. To identify the availability of Personal protective equipment (PPE) for health workers in the different departments of the hospital. To assess the utilization of the PPEs by the health workers in Garowe General Hospital. The data collection method will be a questionnaire procedure and the data analysis method. This will help the researcher to measure different variables in the population of interest at a single point in time.

2.10 Summary:

The most common biological hazards in health settings are; HBV, HCV, HIV, Influenza, TB, and COVID-19, among others. Most of these are caused by NSIs, then droplet/airborne aerosols. The greatest number of needle stick injuries occurs among nurses followed by laboratory employees and doctors as Global health workers reported ⁽⁵²⁾ (Zewde, 2018)

The important elements of prevention are the knowledge, training & distribution of PPE, and taking legally required vaccines for all vaccine-preventable diseases. Extensive use of personal protective equipment can prevent HCWs from possible hazards of biological agents ⁽⁴⁸⁾ (Gonczaryk et al., 2021). As well as other standard precautions such as appropriate hygienic measures (hand washing, respiratory hygiene, environmental hygiene), safe collection and disposal of healthcare waste (e.g., infectious specimens, needle/sharps waste, contaminated linen), and safe handling and cleaning of blood spills and other body fluids. Emergency measures and PEP and follow-up are needed after exposure.

CHAPTER THREE

3.0 METHODOLOGY

Introduction: The chapter presents the research methodology that could be used in the study. This included a description of the Research Design, the Population of the Study, the Study Area, Sample Size Determination, Sampling Procedure, Data Collection Instrument, Data Collection Procedure, Data Analysis Procedure, Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria, and Ethical Considerations,

3.1 Research Design

This was a cross-sectional descriptive study design employing quantitative methods of data collection. The study design was selected because it will help the researcher from measuring different variables in the population of interest at a single point in time.

This cross-sectional descriptive study was conducted in which cases of biological hazard accidents that occurred to healthcare workers were collected, as well as the related factors that could have influenced the occurrence of these accidents, like the availability and utilization of personal protective equipment.

3.2 Population of the Study:

The target population for the study was the HCWs of the Garowe General Hospital. The HCWs, as classified by WHO, include Generalist and specialist medical doctors, nursing and Midwifery professionals, Dentists, Medical and pathology laboratory technicians, pharmacists, cleaners, and other allied health workers. According to the HR director of the hospital ⁽⁵³⁾, the current total number of HCWs at the Garowe General Hospital was 186.

3.3 Study Area

The study was carried out; at Garowe General Hospital, the bigger public hospital located at Garowe, the Capital city of the Nugal region, and Puntland State of Somali Federal Republic. Garowe is located 945 km by road northeast of Mogadishu. The Garowe General Hospital was founded in 1972. The bed capacity of the hospital at this moment is around 120 beds. The hospital consists of 12 departments which are; 1-Emergency Department 2- Surgical Department. 3. Maternity Department. 4. Medical Department 5. Neonatal Department. 6- Laboratory Department 7. Stabilization Center Department 8. X-ray Department 9. Pharmacy Department 10. Pediatric Department 11. Voluntary Counselling Testing Department 12. Operation Theatre Department. The study area has been chosen because of the increasing number of cases of biological hazards among health workers.

3.4 Sample Size Determination

The aim of this literature was: What biological hazards are among healthcare workers in Garowe General Hospital? According to the HR director of GGH ⁽⁵³⁾, the total number of hospital staff was 186. The sample size was calculated based on Yamane's formula below ⁽⁵⁰⁾:

The Yamane formula is given as:

$$n = N / (1 + N(e)^2)$$

where: n = sample size

N = population size

e = level of precision

Given:

$$N = 186$$

$$e = \pm 10\%$$

Substituting these values into the formula:

$$n = 186 / (1 + 186(0.1)^2)$$

$$n = 186 / (1 + 186(0.01))$$

$$n = 186 / (1 + 1.86)$$

$$n = 186 / 2.86$$

$$n = 65.03$$

Rounding up to the nearest whole number, the required sample size is 65.

Therefore, the sample size for the study is 65, assuming a population size of 186 and a precision level of $\pm 10\%$

3.5 Sampling Procedure

The sampling procedure used in this study was a simple random technique to select the respondents. Because everyone in the target population has an equal chance of being included in the study. The sample size was calculated based on Yamane's formula, which is the formula we mentioned before.

3.6 Data collection instrument

A standardized, validated, and self-administered questionnaire was handed over to the selected respondents. The variables included in this study were gender, age, education level, working department, work experience, biohazard exposure, biohazard type, PPE availability, PPE utilization, etc.

3.7 Data Collection Procedure

Before giving out the questionnaires, the researcher fully explained the questions to the respondents. The selected participants were briefed about the study and their willingness to participate was requested through informed consent. After the necessary approval, the data collection process was initiated. The researcher communicated with the selected participants in their workplaces. Collecting data was used in self-administered questionnaires. Each filled-in questionnaire was checked for accuracy and completeness by the researcher immediately.

3.8 Data Analysis Procedure

After collecting the data, it was manually analyzed through tallying and entered into the computer using the Microsoft Excel package and was presented in reliability testing and cleaning the data. A database of the information collected was created. The data was then analyzed using a statistical software package (IBM SPSS). A descriptive analysis of the different variables was performed by calculating the frequencies and percentages. Then it was presented using tables and charts.

3.9 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The study included all the HCWs as classified by the WHO ⁽⁵¹⁾, such as Generalist and specialist medical doctors, nursing and Midwifery professionals, Dentists, Medical and pathology laboratory technicians, pharmacists, cleaners, and other allied health workers, working in various departments/wards at Garowe General Hospital who consented to the study and voluntarily agreeing to participate in it. The HCWs on vacation, those who do not want to participate, and those whom the

researcher could not contact will be considered non-respondents, and they will be excluded from the sampling frame.

3.10 Ethical Consideration:

The questionnaire was anonymous and self-administrated; the HCWs will be informed that participation in the study was non-compulsory.

CHAPTER FOUR:

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

4.1 Results of the questionnaire:

4.1.1 Introduction:

This research was carried out among HCWs working in Garowe General Hospital, located at Garowe, the capital city of Puntland state, Somalia. The number of respondents was 65, with a response rate of 100%.

4.1.2 Results of sociodemographic characteristics:

Table 1: Characteristics of healthcare workers in Garowe General Hospital, Garowe, Puntland, Somalia. 2023 (N: 65).

Variables	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	31	47.7
	Female	34	52.3
	Total	65	100.0
Age in years	18-30	32	49.2
	31-40	30	46.2
	41-50	3	4.6
	Total	65	100.0
Education level	Secondary	16	24.6
	Tertiary	7	10.8
	Decree	36	55.4
	Other	6	9.2
	Total	65	100.0
Work Department	Emergency Dep.	12	18.5
	Female	6	9.2
	Pediatric ward	4	6.2
	Operator/theater	3	4.6
	Other	40	61.5
	Total	65	100.0
HCWs Category	Doctor	23	35.38
	Nurse/midwifery	25	38.46
	Lab. technician	5	7.69
	Other	12	18.46
	Total	65	100.0

Work Experience	Below year	7	10.77
	1-2	23	35.38
	3-5	30	46.15
	6-10	5	7.69
	Total	65	100.0

Table 1: presents the sociodemographic and lifestyle-related characteristics of the sample population. Of the 65 study participants, the majority, 34 (52.3%), were females, and 31 (47.7%) were males. This was near to a previous finding in Somalia (50.8% females) ⁽¹³⁾.

Of the age of the respondents, nearly half of them, 32 (49.2%), were between 18-30 years, 30 (46.2%) were between 31-40 years, and 3 (4.6%) of them were between 41-50 years old. Regarding their level of education, the majority, 36 (55.4%), were at degree level, this is lower than previous findings in Gambella Western Ethiopia (82%) ⁽⁷⁾ and Somalia (74.2% and 9.1% were at bachelor and postgraduate levels) ⁽¹³⁾. 16 (24.6%) were at the high school level, 7 (10.8%) were at the tertiary level, and 6 (9.2%) were at other levels, thus implying that the majority of respondents were university level. According to the work department or ward of the respondents, 12 (18.5%) were in Emergency Dep., 6 (9.2%) were in the female department, 4 (6.2%) were in the pediatric ward, 3 (4.6%) were in the operation theater, while the majority 40 (61.5%) work at other departments of the hospital. Regarding the HCWs category, 25 (38.5%) were nurses/midwifery, 23 (35.4%) were doctors, 5 (7.7%) were Laboratory technicians, while the 12 (18.5%) were the other staff of the hospital. The work experience of the participants shows that 7 (10.8%) of them had an experience of less than one year, 23 (35.4%) had an experience of 1-2 years, 30 (46.2%) had an experience of 3-5 years, while 6 (7.7%) had 6-10 years. This implies the majority of respondents had 3-5 years of experience.

Figure 2: Gender of participants**4.1.3-**

Figure 2: Gender of participants: 52.3% were females, and 47.7% were males. This shows that the majority of participants were females.

Figure 3: Age of participants in years

Figure 3: Age of participants in years; 49.2% were age group of 18-30, 46.2% were 31-40, and 4.6% were age group of 41-50.

Figure 4: Education level of participants.

Figure 4: shows the education level of participants: 55.4% were at degree level, 24.6% were at the secondary level, 10.8% were at tertiary level, and 9.2% were at other levels.

Figure 5: Work department of participants

Figure 5: Work departments of participants: 18.5% work in the emergency depart., 9.2% in the female department, 6.2% in the pediatric depart., and 4.6% operation theater dep. While 61.5% work in other departments.

Figure 6: HCWs Category

Figure 6: Healthcare workers category; This figure shows that the majority (38.5%) of the participants were Nurses/midwifery, 35.4% were doctors, 7.7% were Lab technicians, and 18.5% were others.

Figure 7: Work experience in years

Figure 7: shows that the work experience of the majority of participants (46.2%) was 3-5 years, 35.4% was 1-2 years, 10.8% below a year, and 7.7% was 6-10 years.

4.1.3 Results of common biological hazards faced by the Study Participants.

Table 2: Most common biological hazards among healthcare workers at GGH (N= 65)

Variables	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Have you ever taken sessions on biohazards?	Yes	54	83.1
	No	11	16.9
	Total	65	100.0
What are the most common biohazards experienced in your hospital?	Blood	28	43.08
	Vomit	17	26.15
	Liquor	5	7.69
	Aerosols/droplets	11	16.92
	Stool or urine	4	6.15
	Total	65	100.0
Have you ever been exposed to any of these hazards in the hospital?	NSIs	23	35.38
	Cuts and lacerations	4	6.2
	Droplet/airborne infections	24	36.92
	Direct contact with specimen/biohazardous materials	12	18.46
	Cross-contamination from soiled materials	2	3.08
	Total	65	100.0
Have you been exposed to HB, HC, HIV/AIDS, TB, and Influenza infections during your working time?	Yes	33	50.8
	NO	32	49.2
	Total	65	100.0
In case of exposure, are you provided with post-exposure prophylaxis?	Yes	32	49.2
	No	33	50.8
	Total	65	100.0
Are you immunized against these diseases?	Hepatitis B	20	30.8
	TB	27	41.5
	Influenza	1	1.5
	All	17	26.2
	Total	65	100.0

How often do you wash your hands while at work?	Before and after medical procedures	00	00
	After removing the gloves	00	00
	After handling soiled materials	00	00
	Before and after dealing with each patient	00	00
	All	65	100
	Total	65	100.0

Table 2 above reported that the majority, 54 (83.1%), of respondents, took sessions or courses on biological hazards, while 11 (16.9%) did not attend such sessions. According to the most common biohazard they experienced in the hospital, the majority, 28 (43.1%) of participants experienced blood, while 17 (26.2%) experienced vomit, 11 (16.9%) experienced aerosols/cough droplets, 5 (7.7%) experienced liquor, and 4 (6.2%) experienced stool or urine. 23 (35.4%) of the respondents were exposed to NSIs, 4 (6.2%) were exposed to cuts and lacerations, 24 (36.9%) were exposed to Droplet/airborne infections, 12 (18.5%) direct contact with specimen/biohazardous materials, this is lower than a study done in Southwest Nigeria (58.6%)⁽⁵⁾. 2 (3.1%) of the respondents were exposed to cross-contamination from soiled materials. 33(50.8%) of the participants reported exposure to infectious diseases such as HB, HC, HIV/AIDS, TB, and Influenza infections, while 32 (49.2%) of respondents were not exposed to such diseases. Of those exposed to those infections, 32 (49.2% of total HCWs) reported that; they were provided with post-exposure prophylaxis, while only 1 (1.5%) did not receive PEP. Of most of the respondents, 27 (41.5%) were immunized against TB, 20 (30.8%) were vaccinated against Hepatitis B, 1 (1.5%) was immunized against influenza, and 17 (26.2%) had taken all vaccinations. Of all the participants, 65(100%) reported that; they washed their hands before and after medical

procedures; after removing the gloves; after handling soiled materials, and before and after dealing with each patient.

4.1.4: Results of availability and utilization of PPE by the HCWs at GGH.

Table 3: Availability and utilization of PPE by the study participants (N= 65)

Variables	Category	Frequency	Percentage
How can biological hazards be prevented?	Masks	00	00
	Gloves	00	00
	Protective clothing	00	00
	Eye/face shields	00	00
	Respirators	65	100.0
	All PPE		
Are all personal protective equipment (PPE) available at the hospital?	Yes	63	96.9
	No	2	3.1
	Total	65	100.0
Do you believe that there are lack or shortage of PPE in the hospital?	Yes	2	3.1
	No	63	96.9
	Total	65	100.0
Do you wear all necessary PPE when dealing with patients, biochemical wastes, or specimens?	Yes	62	95.4
	No	3	4.6
	Total	65	100.0
Did you select PPE correctly?	Yes	65	100
	No	00	00
	Total	65	100.0
Did you remove PPE correctly?	Yes	65	100
	No	00	00
	Total	65	100.0
Did you perform hand hygiene after removing your gloves, gown, masks, or eye protection?	Yes	65	100
	NO	00	00
	Total	65	100.0
Do you believe that lack/shortage of PPE can contribute to biological hazards?	Yes	65	100
	No	00	00
	Total	65	100.0

Table 3 above reported when asked the respondents which of these materials can be prevented biological hazards: Masks, Gloves, Protective clothing, Eye/face shields, Respirators, or All PPE? Of all the participants [65 (100%)] chose the option; All PPE. Regarding the availability of all PPE at the hospital, the majority of respondents, 63 (96.9%), agreed; with their availability. When we asked the participants if they believed in the shortage or lack of PPE in the hospital: the majority, 63 (96.9%), did not believe in it, while 2 (3.1%) believed in it. When dealing with patients, biochemical wastes, or specimens, the majority, 62 (95.4%), of participants wore all necessary PPE, while only 3 (4.6%) said they didn't wear all the needed PPE. For selecting and removing the PPE, all 65 (100%) participants selected and wore off the PPE correctly. After removing the gloves, gown, masks, or eye protection, all 65 (100%) perform hand hygiene. All 65(100%) of the respondents believe that lack/shortage of PPE can contribute to biological hazards

4.2 Discussion:

Healthcare settings, like other high-risk workplaces, are characterized by high levels of exposure to hazardous factors that pose significant threats to the health and life of healthcare workers. Unsafe work environments for healthcare staff and high doctor-patient ratios increase the risk of exposure to bloodborne and droplet/airborne pathogens, leading to preventable infections. This study revealed that greater than half (50.8%) of the healthcare workers encountered at least one type of the most common biological hazard (infectious disease), such as HB, HC, HIV/AIDS, TB, and influenza infections, before the survey date. This finding was nearly similar to a study done in Jugol Hospital in Eastern Ethiopia (52.7%)⁽⁵²⁾ and greater than a study done in Gambella Town Western Ethiopia (41%)⁽⁷⁾ and Uganda (39.5%)⁽⁶⁾. On the contrary, the current finding was lower than other studies done in Southern India (81.5%)⁽³⁰⁾, Northern Saudi Arabia (68.5%)⁽³⁸⁾, and

Southwest Nigeria (70.7%)⁽⁵⁾. The variations in the magnitude of biological hazards among the HCWs might be because of the difference in the health system characteristics, the type of HCWs included in the studies, and their training. Healthcare workers in higher institutions or specialty hospitals were relatively more exposed than workers in lower institutions such as primary hospitals and health centers. In addition, clinical staff was exposed to biological risks more than non-clinical staff. In this study: the majority of the participants are doctors and nurses, and the majority (83.1%) of the participants attended courses on biological hazards and how can be prevented.

In this study, more than 1/3 of healthcare workers (35.4%,) reported as they had been exposed to NSIs. This finding was similar to a study done in Northern Saudi Arabia (34.5%)⁽³⁸⁾. And greater than a study done in Gambella Western Ethiopia (28.2%)⁽⁷⁾. And lower than the result found in a study conducted on the Jugol Hospital Eastern Ethiopia (54.1%)⁽⁵²⁾ Serbia (60.6%)⁽⁹⁾, and Ondo City Southwest Nigeria (75.4%)⁽⁵⁾. In the current study, 6.2% of respondents were exposed to cuts and lacerations. This finding was lower than those done in Saudi Arabia (19.4%)⁽³⁸⁾ and Ondo City Southwest Nigeria (60%)⁽⁵⁾.

In this study, 43.1% of HCWs were exposed to blood contact. This finding is greater than the result conducted at the Jugol Hospital (34.5%)⁽⁵²⁾ and Gambella Western Ethiopia (28.2%)⁽⁷⁾. 36.9% of HCWs in this study were exposed to droplet/airborne infections. This finding is greater than the result found in Northern Saudi (31.1%)⁽³⁸⁾ and Gambella Western Ethiopia (17.9%)⁽⁷⁾. On the contrary, it is lower than a study done in Ondo City Southwest Nigeria (60%)⁽⁵⁾.

On the vaccination status, 41.5% of HCWs were vaccinated against TB, and 30.8% against Hepatitis B, this is lower than a study done in Serbia (50.2%)⁽⁹⁾. 1.5% were vaccinated against influenza, and 26.2% against all.

In this study, the majority of participant HCWs, (96.9%) said that all personal protective equipment (PPE) is available at the hospital. It was probably because of the only state-run hospital in Garowe, the capital of Puntland state, and therefore all equipment was provided to it. It is also possible that since many refugee camps are around the city, and the only hospital they have access to go is the government hospital, aid agencies may equip and donate to the hospital.

In this study, 95.4% of respondents wear all necessary PPE when dealing with patients, biochemical wastes, specimens, etc. On the contrary, the current finding was greater than another study finding from Uganda (57.5%) ⁽⁶⁾. In the current research, all the healthcare workers (100%) reported that; they washed their hands before and after medical procedures; after removing the gloves; after handling soiled materials, and before/after dealing with each patient. While another study conducted in Uganda ⁽⁶⁾ showed that most health workers washed their hands before and after every procedure (79.5%) and after handling soiled materials (68.5%); After removing gloves (66.5%), Before and after handling each patient (68.0%); after handling biological samples (68.0%); and before and after handling hazardous materials (53.0%). These differences might be due to the availability of enough hand-washing facilities and water, differences in the capacity and type of health institutions, the composition of health workers considered, and their education level. In the study area, the majority of HCWs were at the university level. In addition, the study period and study participants might contribute to the difference in the magnitude of PPE utilization and performing hand hygiene.

CHAPTER FIVE:

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS.

The conclusion of the study based on the study results is important suggestions and recommendations were presented about the objectives of the work.

5.1 Conclusion:

- The majority of HCW participants, 34 (52.3%), were females, and the majority of participants were age groups of 18-30 and 31-40 (49.2% and 46.2%, respectively)
- The majority of staff member respondents (55.4%) were at university levels.

The most common biological hazards among HCWs:

- The majority of HCWs, (83.1%), attended courses on biological hazards.
- More than half [33 (50.8%)] of the healthcare workers encountered at least one type of the most common biological hazard (infectious disease) such as HB, HC, HIV/AIDS, TB, and Influenza infections, and 32 (98.5% of those who exposed to that infections) had provided post-exposure prophylaxis.
- The most common biohazard they experienced in the hospital was Blood (43.1%), and vomit (26.2%)
- HCWs exposed to NSIs (35.4%), cuts and lacerations (6.2%), droplet/airborne infections (36.9%), and direct contact with specimen/biohazardous materials (18.5%).
- The participants were vaccinated against Hepatitis B (30.8%), TB (41.5%), Influenza (1.5%), and all of them 26.2%.

Availability and utilization of PPE

- All PPE was available at the hospital according to the majority (96.9%) of HCWs, and 95.4% of healthcare workers utilize all necessary PPE when they are dealing with patients, specimens, medical wastes, etc.
- They all perform hand washing before and after medical procedures; after removing PPE; after handling soiled materials, and before and after dealing with each patient.
- They believed that wearing PPE can protect against biological hazards, and lack of it can contribute to Biological hazard incident rises.

5.2 RECOMMENDATIONS:

The Ministries of Health and the hospitals-managers should consider the following recommendations to protect the basic rights and well-being of HCWs.

- All HCWs should receive periodic courses to educate them on universal health and safety precautions to promote the safety of HCWs and their patients.
- A comprehensive vaccination program should be introduced in all hospitals and other health facilities to vaccinate HCWs against vaccine-preventable diseases to reduce their acquisition risk.
- Post-exposure prophylaxis should be made available to HCWs who sustain Sharp/NS injuries, aerosol/droplet exposure, and other biohazardous exposures.
- Health settings should have adequate medical waste disposal systems to dispose of waste.
- Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) should be made available to HCWs and trained on how and when to use it.

- Healthcare settings should establish occupational risk monitoring systems for healthcare professionals to identify early warnings and respond appropriately to these risks.

5.3 LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

The study was limited to Garowe General Hospital only therefore, the results cannot be generalized to all Garowe hospitals and health services. As it was a cross-sectional study, it's not enough to make the final decision, so; further studies and investigations are needed to be done in the future.

5.4 Future Research

- ❖ Knowledge, Attitude, and practice of biological hazards among Health care workers.
- ❖ Identifying factors of influence on biological hazards among Health care workers.

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- 53- Dr. Du'aysane Isse Ahmed, HR Director of Garowe General Hospital.

Appendix I: Questionnaire

Dear respondents, I am a student at Accord University preparing my thesis for a master's in tropical medicine and infectious diseases. This questionnaire has been designed for data collection concerning the study of common biological hazards among healthcare workers and the availability & utilization of personal protective equipment in Garowe general hospital. The purpose of this questionnaire is for academic reasons, not for money; therefore, I kindly request you answer these questions to the way best of your knowledge. Instructions: Do not write your name on the questionnaire. Please provide precise information to your level best. All information will be private. Confidentiality will be adhered to when handling the provided information. Please tick in the box provided to the best of your knowledge. Thank you

Section A: Sociodemographic Characteristics of the Participants:

Q1: Gender: Male Female

Q2: Age: 18-30 31-40 41-50 51-65

Q3: Education level:

Primary Secondary: Tertiary: Degree:
Other

Q4: Working Ward/Department:

Emergency Dep.

Male ward

Female ward

Pediatric ward

Operator/theater

Other

Q5: HCWs category (Staff);

Doctor

Nursing/Midwifery

Lab technicians

Other

Q6: Work experience, in years: <1 year 1-2 years 3-5

6-10 years >10

Section B: Biological hazards faced by the HCWs:

Q1: Have you ever taken sessions on biological risk?

Yes No

Q2: What are the most common biological hazards experienced in your hospital?

1- Blood

2- Vomit

3- Liquor

4- Aerosols, cough droplets

5- Stool or urine

Q3: Have you ever been exposed to any of the hazards listed below during your work time in this hospital?

- 1- Needle stick injuries. []
- 2- Cuts and lacerations. []
- 3- Droplet/Airborne infections. []
- 4- Direct contact with contaminated specimens/biohazardous materials. []
- 5- Cross-contamination from soiled materials..... []

Q4: Have you been exposed to any of these diseases during your work time in this hospital: HB, HC, HIV/AIDS, TB, or Influenza infections?

Yes [] No []

Q5: In case of exposure to any of these diseases, are you provided with post-exposure prophylaxis?

Yes [] No []

Q6: Are you immunized against the following diseases?

- 1- Hepatitis B... []
- 2- Tuberculosis..... []
- 3- Influenza []
- 4- All []
- 5- None []

Q7: How often do you wash your hands while at work in the hospital?

- 1- Before and after medical procedures..... []

2- After removing the gloves..... []

3- After handling soiled materials..... []

4- Before and after dealing with each patient... []

Section C: Availability and utilization of PPE by HCWs in the hospital.

Q8: How can biological hazards be prevented?

1- Masks [] 2- Gloves [] 3- Protective Clothing []

4- Eye/Face shields [] 5- Respirators: [] 6- All PPE: []

Q9: Are all personal protective equipment available at the hospital?

Yes [] No []

Q10: Do you believe that there are lack or shortage of PPE in the hospital?

Yes [] No []

Q11: Do you wear all necessary PPE when dealing with patients, biomedical waste, or specimens?

Yes [] No []

Q12: Did you select PPE correctly?

Yes [] No []

Q13: Did you remove PPEs correctly?

Yes [] No []

Q14: Did you perform hand hygiene after removing your gloves, gown, mask, or eye protection?

Yes []

No []

Q15: Do you believe that lack/shortage of PPE can contribute to biological hazards?

Yes []

No []

Thank you very much for your cooperation!!

Appendix 2: Work Plan.

No	Tasks	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	March	April	May
1	Title selection							
2	Proposal Writing							
3	Thesis writing							
4	Data Collection							
5	Data Analysis							
6	Submission of Thesis							
7	Defense Date							

Appendix 3. Budget

NO	ITEM	DESCRIPTION	AMOUNT
1	Copying	Amount paid in copy	\$13
2	Transportation	Amount paid in transportation	\$20
3	Printing of thesis	Amount paid in published	\$15
	Total		\$48

Appendix 4: Map of Garowe City, Nugal Region, Puntland State, Somalia.

